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PROBLEMS OF SYNONYMY AND ANTONYMY OF TERMS – THEORETICAL REVIEW
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ANNOTATION

In the following article, we will discuss such linguistic properties of the language of special purposes as synonymy, antonymy and polysemy. If in the general vocabulary these phenomena are presented sequentially, then in the special vocabulary they have their own characteristics. So, unambiguity has always been singled out as the desired requirements for terms, when one word has one meaning. This means that the term has no polysemantic relations, synonyms, antonyms. Modern studies of terminological units prove that in practice the situation is different. Within special areas of knowledge, there is a continuous replenishment and updating of lexical units, often ahead of the development of general vocabulary, where there is no urgent need to replenish and expand the vocabulary.

Key words: term, synonymy, antonymy, polysemy, lexicon, linguistic research, terminological units.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада биз махсус мақсадли тилнинг синонимия, антонимия ва полисемия каби лингвистик хусусиятларини муҳокама қиламиз. Агар умумий луғатда бу ҳодисалар кетма-кет берилган бўлса, махсус луғатда улар ўзига хос хусусиятларга эга. Шундай қилиб, бир сўз бир маънога эга бўлганда, терминларга қўйиладиган талаб сифатида ҳар доим бир маънолилиқ ажратиб кўрсатилган. Демак, атаманинг полисемантик алоқалари, синонимлари, антонимлари йўқ. Терминологик бирликларнинг замонавий тадқиқотлари амалда вазият бошқача эканлигини кўрсатади. Муайян билим соҳаларида лексик бирликларнинг доимий равишда тўлдирилиши ва янгиланиши мавжуд бўлиб, аксарият ҳолларда умумий лексика ривожланишидан олдин луғатни тўлдириш ва кенгайтириш эҳтиёжини келтириб чиқаради.

Калит сўзлар: термин, синонимия, антонимия, полисемия, лексика, лингвистик тадқиқотлар, терминологик бирликлар.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье мы обсудим лингвистические особенности языка специального назначения, такие как синонимия, антонимия и полисемия. Если в общем словаре эти события даны последовательно, то в специальном словаре они имеют свои особенности. Таким образом, когда слово имеет единственное значение, однозначность всегда выделяется как требование к терминам. Итак, термин не имеет многозначных отношений, синонимов, антонимов. Современные исследования терминологических единиц показывают, что на практике дело обстоит иначе. В специальных областях знаний происходит постоянное пополнение и обновление лексических единиц, нередко до освоения общей лексики, что создает здесь потребность в пополнении и расширении словарного запаса.

Ключевые слова: термин, синонимия, антонимия, полисемия, лексика, лингвистическое исследование, терминологические единицы.

The increase in the number of terminological units is often due to the processes of terminology of commonly used words, as well as various word-formation processes. When analyzing the semantic structure of a term, it seems relevant to refer to the main lexico-semantic phenomena occurring in term systems - synonymy, antonymy, polysemy.

For the implementation of the communicative and expressive function of the language, accuracy, expressiveness, differentiation of concepts and a variety of vocabulary that could convey subtle shades of thought and feelings are necessary. The implementation of all these functions leads to the emergence of synonyms and, as a result, the phenomenon of synonymy.

Synonymy is inherent in both common and special vocabulary. According to the definition of the Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary, synonymy is "a type of semantic relations of linguistic units, consisting in the complete or partial coincidence of their meanings. Synonymy reflects the properties of the objective world in the language. The linguistic nature of synonymy is determined by the varying degree of semantic similarity of linguistic units and is explained by the asymmetry of the sign and meaning, their unstable balance.

In synonyms, a more subtle differentiation of concepts is fixed, their features are clarified, the attitude of the speaker to the subject of speech is expressed, and the richness of the experience of the people is fixed. Therefore, "it is necessary to consider synonyms not so much as words that can replace each other, but as words that clarify the thought and attitude to what is being expressed".

According to D.N. Shmelev, synonyms are words of the same part of speech, the meanings of which contain both identical and different elements. In some contexts, synonyms can be interchangeable, while in others, on the contrary, incompatibility of features is found. "Synonyms can be recognized as words that are opposed only by such semantic features that in certain contexts become irrelevant". Since the number of identical semantic elements for different rows of words is not always the same, we are talking about different degrees of synonymy for different words.

According to Z.A. Kharitonchik, "the differences between synonyms do not pass along the line of their lexical meanings, taken in their entirety, but concern only some semantic components of lexical meanings with the obligatory generality of other parts of the structure of lexical meaning.

Expressions correlated with one concept form a "series of terms", the members of this family are synonymous terms. "Synonyms are words with similar, but not identical meanings, each word in the synonymic series has its own" group of meanings".

According to M.V. Nikitin, synonymy is "the phenomenon of switching in the meaning of signs from one meaningful aspect to another, namely, switching the cognitive content of a sign to a plane of pragmatic meaning". This semantic transition of the sign from the cognitive plane to the pragmatic one is based on the correlation between cognitive and pragmatic aspects of the sign. Thus, synonymy is observed when "synonyms are equated to the dominant of the synonymic series, differing from it by pragmatic additions".

Giving a definition of the concept of a synonym Y.D. Apresyan writes that "words that completely coincide in meaning are increasingly considered as lexical doublets, variants, etc., and words that certainly differ in meaning are beginning to be considered genuine synonyms". Y.D.

Apresyan distinguishes four groups of differences: semantic, evaluative, differences in semantic associations, differences in logical accents.

In common vocabulary, synonymy is considered as a positive phenomenon that creates expressiveness of speech and stylistic coloring of texts, however, in terminology, the phenomenon of synonymy is usually interpreted as a lack of terminology, which leads to redundancy in the means of naming concepts and, as a result, to difficulties in mutual understanding. "The problem of synonymy of terms, i.e. the use of several special lexical units for naming one concept is one of the most important problems of terminology".

We believe that "even a slight difference in words that are close in meaning indicates that we are dealing with two close, but nonetheless different concepts and, therefore, different terms. If the terms mean the same concept, then they, as a rule, are absolute equivalents in meaning".

Depending on how the elements of a synonymic pair differ from each other, ideographic (semantic) synonyms are distinguished, when synonyms have different shades of meaning, stylistic, differing in stylistic coloring and scope, and equivalent (absolute). Since the goal of scientific speech is to convey information, and not to achieve stylistic effects, stylistic synonyms in terminology are rare. Equivalent or absolute terms-synonyms we will call doublets. We believed that one of the important tasks of streamlining any terminology is to distinguish between synonyms and doublets, where "synonyms are different words, and doublets are variants of the same word."

According to B.N. Golovin, "specialists are always interested in the fact that the meaning of the term is clear and one and only. This saves the participants in communication from disagreement in the understanding and application of the same terms, reduces losses in the perception and assimilation of information". However, despite the fact that ideal requirements are imposed on the term - unambiguity and accuracy, the specificity of scientific thinking is such that it does not allow them to be met. "Thinking and the process of labor development of the world continuously gives rise to a change in the boundaries of established concepts, especially in the field of theory, and creates new concepts that require verbal, terminological designation and expression". As M.V. Nikitin "synonymy is not only a vocabulary of language, but even more a communicative-pragmatic speech action".

Thus, despite the desire for "ideal" terms as tools of cognition, in practice they often turn out to be far from ideal. Terminologists noted that "in all areas of terminological vocabulary there are a large number of synonyms, and some types of synonymy of terms are of a regular nature". It seems that the long-term practice of terminology, which confirms the existence of actual synonymy of terms, cannot be rejected, and one should study terms and term systems as they are, and analyze the synonymy of terms in the course of studying lexico-semantic phenomena in terminology. In this paper, we will understand synonymous terms as terms of the same language with a similar but not identical meaning.

In addition to the phenomenon of synonymy, semantic relations in the lexical system of the language are complemented by antonymy. Antonymic relations of terminological units are one of the manifestations of the systemic nature of terminology. In our mind antonyms are words with opposite meanings, that is, correlated with concepts that have opposite qualities". "Antonymy belongs to the most important semantic relations that form the simplest type of structure, or a contrastive set".

M.V. Nikitin points out the following paradoxical fact: despite the fact that the meanings of antonyms are opposite, these words "are among the closest semantic rapprochements in the vocabulary". The abundance of units opposite in meaning is associated with the desire of a person to place the accumulated experience on the polar points of the scales. As a result of this process, groups of lexical meanings are formed. If the speaker knows the meaning of one of the members of the group, he can understand the meaning of all the other members of this group, since the members of the opposition are not presented to the addressee without the presence of this opposition.

According to Uzbek linguists "antonyms have opposite or reverse, but not contradictory meanings". Antonyms are characterized by a semantic commonality, which can manifest itself in the "correlation of meanings", belonging to the same "lexico-semantic paradigm", the expression of the same generic concept. "It is obligatory for antonyms to designate qualitative features that allow

grading, so that between the two poles of a feature whose names are the corresponding antonyms, a middle (zero) term is always possible”.

The phenomenon of antonymy, manifested in the existence of words with opposite meanings, is widespread in the language of science.

The prerequisite for the emergence of antonymy is the fact that the differences that exist in objective reality are reflected in the language in the form of antonymic meanings. According to the history of thought, concepts are born in pairs. Any concept that arises in a language carries its own opposite.

In terminology, antonymy helps to highlight the extreme points of the terminological field and "acts as one of the regular principles for naming concepts with opposite content".

It is necessary to answer the question under what conditions the signs are considered opposite. Opposite is that which is maximally different in terms of the feature underlying the comparison. So, hot and cold are based on a common parameter: temperature is a deviation from a certain standard. Similarly, hard and soft are based on a common parameter: tactility - a deviation from a certain norm.

In this article, we believe that in order for two concepts-meanings to be considered opposite, it is necessary that their content either be exhausted by opposite semantic features, or, if they have a common generic feature, their specific (differential) features should be opposite. Thus, words enter into antonymous relations if their lexical meanings are characterized by the presence of opposite semantic features.

So, as a result of linguistic research, important criteria of the terminological system were identified, which determine its features as a subsystem of the literary language: synonymy and antonymy.

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